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Information support of the national security of the state in the context of globalization

The article reveals the issues of information support of the national security of the state. Analyzed various scientific approaches in the definition of the concept of national security. Characterized by the role of information resources and information in general in the formation of the national security of the state.

Keywords: *information support, national security, government-management processes, information communications.*

The relevance of the study is characterized by the ever-increasing role of the information sphere, which is a collection of information, information infrastructure, entities engaged in the collection, formation, dissemination and use of information, as well as a system for regulating the resulting social relations. The information sphere, being a system-forming factor in the life of society, actively influences the state of political, economic, government and other security components of modern states, which significantly depends on information security, and in the course of technical progress, this dependence is increasingly increasing.

In addition, in modern conditions, the role of information in the development of government and management processes is increasingly increasing and as a result,

information threats to the security of individuals, society, and the state increase. In this sense, the latter act as objects and subjects of information security at the intergovernmental, regional, national-state levels.

Problems and ways of information security of the state are not the latest in terms of research interest. They are constantly considered in the works of domestic and foreign authors in the context of various scientific interests. National security issues, various aspects of its security were considered in the scientific works of A. Vasilyuva, A. Vozzhenikova, N. N. Winner, V. Stepanova, I. Panarin, G. Pocheptsova, S. Chukut, T. Schubert, A. Fomin and others. At the same time, in our opinion, the questions of the correlation of information aspects in the formation of the national security of modern states in the context of state management problems have not yet found sufficient coverage in the scientific literature.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the problem of the information security of the state as the most important component of the national security of modern states in the context of actively occurring globalization processes in the world.

In modern conditions, achieving the required level of national security requires a clear understanding of all the threats, real and potential, that face modern states.

This makes it necessary to continuously obtain reliable and complete information not only about the threats and the degree of their danger, but also about the possibilities of influencing them in order to eliminate, neutralize or reduce their danger. This situation can be achieved within the framework of the organization and effective implementation of information security of national security.

In our opinion, the problem of information security of national security is only technical at first glance: it has specific philosophical, economic, state-administrative, sociocultural aspects, since the presence or absence of information, its rational use or non-use entails enormous destructive consequences for person, society and state. In foreign and domestic science, as well as government practice, the term "national security" began to be actively used in the early 90s of the XX century. In the first

quarter of the twenty-first century, research is actively carried out related to ensuring the national security of the Ukrainian state.

All of them in one way or another affect the study of the category “national security”.

At the same time, the whole diversity of definitions of national security somehow reflects its essential and functional aspects and differs from each other by a set of characteristics and components.

National security is understood as the state of protection of the national interests of a country in the face of real and potential threats [1, p.40-43].

National security is a state in which the state protects the country's national interests in a broad sense, including political, social, economic, military, environmental, government and management aspects, risks associated with foreign economic activity, the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, and the prevention of threats to the spiritual and intellectual values of the people.

In this definition, "security acts as the activity of people, society, state, world community of nations to identify (study), prevent, weaken, eliminate (eliminate) and repel dangers and threats that can destroy them, deprive them of the fundamental material and spiritual values unacceptable (unacceptable objectively and subjectively) damage, close the path for progressive development "[2], and in this sense, it's more likely not about security itself, but about determining its security.

Since security, from our point of view, is primarily a state that has certain parameters and characteristics, and the real activity, first of all, of state bodies is aimed at achieving and maintaining this state. It should be noted that this state is not static, but is in dynamics.

The concept of "national security" is of a concrete historical nature, that is, it has past, present and future, and is viewed in space and time, which is very important for organizing and implementing its information support.

Considering the above, national security is a state of protection of the vital interests of an individual, society, state from external and internal threats and dangers, ensuring their reliable existence, competitiveness and dynamic development.

This interpretation of the concept of "national security" allows us to distinguish two main areas of its security: firstly, protection against threats and dangers; secondly, the creation of conditions for reliable existence and dynamic development. The first involves the creation and operation of a system of opposition, an adequate response to threats and dangers, the second is the activity of creating and accumulating material and spiritual potentials and using them to realize national interests.

This, in our opinion, implies the proposition that national security has at least three aspects:

activity (national security as a set of activities of subjects to ensure it);

value (national security as a set of values important for the individual, the state and society);

personified-individual (national security as a result of the activities embodied in a person).

This approach demonstrates the need and importance of improving information processes. This means that the achievement of security is always associated with the study of relevant information (for example: the degree of threat and danger, the possibilities of eliminating them, neutralizing or reducing them; the realization of the interests of an individual, society, state; the mechanism of their realization, etc.) in which reflects the elements of activities to achieve its goals.

The definition of the national security structure is important for information support, which makes it possible to identify both the types of information circulating in the field of national security and the system of information links in it, as well as to identify the subjects and objects of national security that need information.

In the scientific literature there are several approaches in determining the elements of national security.

Thus, according to the well-known scientist V. Legasov, based on the nature of the sources of danger, seven such elements can be distinguished: 1) military-political, implying the survival of a nation, preventing military confrontation at any cost; 2) industrial - protection from stationary or emergency impact of powerful industrial objects; 3) economic - prevention of further inefficient management of the country; 4) political - non-admission of braking of processes of democratization and publicity; 5) national-cultural - preservation and protection of historical traditions and heritage, the prevention of national conflicts; 6) humanitarian - protection of human values and 7) social and political - protection of social achievements of the Soviet society [3, pp.116-118.].

Another researcher B.Porfiriev believes that national security includes the following elements:

human life and health - environmental (including medical) safety;

socio-political rights and living conditions of citizens, social groups;

the political structure of society as a whole - socio-political, state security;

socio-economic rights and living conditions of citizens, social groups,

societies as a whole - social and economic security;

environmental rights and living conditions of citizens, social groups, society as a whole - environmental safety;

national and cultural rights and living conditions of citizens, social groups, society as a whole - national and cultural security;

military (defense) potential of society (nation) as a whole,

national borders - military-political,

state security;

the economic potential of the society (nation) as a whole is economic security [4, p.11-12].

Another fairly common point of view belongs to the Russian Scientist V. Mukhin, who considers the entire set of threats to national security. Depending on the

vital interests of the individual, the state and society, they threaten, speak about economic, political, legal, military, environmental, informational, etc. threats and relevant types of security [5, p.27].

Based on the above, these types of security (economic, political, legal, military, environmental, information) are the main structural elements of national security.

Some authors single out the system of personal security, the state security system, the public security system, as structural elements of the national security system [2].

It seems that the latter is legitimate when it comes to the national security system, and these structural elements, although they are complete systems, are subsystems of a higher order system — the national security system.

Such an approach to determining the structure of national security has its own set of information links, which, in our opinion, largely form the system of national security itself.

Without considering all the main types of links that form the integrity, it is necessary to note the materiality of the information links of the national security system.

Information communications in the field of national security are as complex and multi-level as its structure. In a generalized form, they can be represented as a set of groups of interrelations.

First, it is the exchange of information between the subjects of ensuring national security, ensuring the formation of the organizational integrity of the system.

Secondly, informational links between people whose activities are directly and indirectly related to ensuring the functioning of the national security system.

Thirdly, informational links between the technical components of the system, since part of the information functions that are redundant for a person but necessary for ensuring national security, are transferred in modern conditions to various technical means.

In addition, informational links can be divided into two groups.

The first group consists of informative information links characterized by structural (related) information. These are links between security elements; between the internal elements of each type of security; between each type of security and the external environment (the external environment here refers to the national interests of other countries), etc.

The second group is represented by functional informational links characterized by operational information. These include subject-object (between subjects, objects, between subjects and objects, as well as within them) connections; connections between subjects, objects and sources of threats, as well as with the external environment.

At the same time, the entire aggregate of informational links in relation to national security can be divided into external and internal informational links.

All these links do not exist isolated from each other, but intersecting among themselves, form a system of informational relations, which is one of the most important factors determining the effectiveness of the functioning of the national security system. Emphasizing the importance of information sharing for the development and functioning of social systems.

N. Wiener called informational connections “cement that holds society together” [6, p.31], and A. Berg and B. Biryukov wrote that “if living beings did not have senses or other “devices” of information capture, or there would be no “information field”, life on Earth could neither arise nor exist [7, p.350].

It is obvious that the system of ensuring national security cannot arise, much less function as a whole without the organization of information processes inside it. The need for such an organization is due to many factors, the most important of which is the need to develop management objectives, in our case, governing the state and get the means to achieve them, the needs of self-organization: the system.

Based on the above, it follows that without proper organization of informational links, it is impossible to ensure the expedient behavior of the system in changing conditions, it is impossible to connect different-quality components into a single, permanently functioning whole and keep the system in constant readiness to perform emerging tasks.

And the lack of information exchange between the components of the system (public administration system) for ensuring national security will inevitably lead to the disintegration of the functional type of relations between them, the separation of the system and its death.

Thus, the presented system of information links makes it possible to identify information flows, determine their orientation and content, which makes it possible to rationally use information resources and the potential to provide the subjects of national security with the most complete, reliable and timely information.

The presence of such a complex, dynamic structure of national security, as well as the system of information links discussed above, predetermines a large number of information flows.

It seems that they can be classified for the same reasons as informational links. Let us briefly discuss the characteristics of the most important. These, in our opinion, include: internal and external; ascending, descending and horizontal; direct and reverse.

The external flow of information is the movement of information from the global (universal), regional, as well as national security systems to a specific national security system. This stream links the national security system with a system of external hazards and threats, as well as with security systems of equal and higher order. The internal flow links the structures that ensure national security among themselves, as well as with the subjects and the system of internal hazards and threats. Information here reflects all aspects of state-management, economic, legal and other activities of

national security entities to ensure stability, the realization of the vital interests of both individuals and society, and the state.

In the internal and external flows there is the most diverse information in content and form (for example, in content: state management, legal, military, social, etc.; in form - documented, electronic, oral, etc.).

Upstream - represents the movement of information from the bottom up. It is formed by individuals, leaders of the lower levels of government and management, political and public organizations, other grassroots structures. It reflects the results of the implementation and protection of the vital interests of individuals, social groups, teams. This stream reaches the upper levels of political and state power as the most important element of the national security system. The downstream is the movement of information from the upper levels of the national security system to its foundation, from the highest levels of political and state power to an individual, social group or collective.

Horizontal flow circulates at the same hierarchical level of the national security system. This is the flow of interaction. For the sphere of state management of the national security system, direct and reverse information flows are characteristic. Their presence contributes to the preservation of dynamic equilibrium by the system. Direct (from the subject of management to the object) and reverse (from the object of management to the subject) information flows carry vast amounts of information about the functioning of the national security system. It is the information of these flows that makes it possible to correct the correctness of decision-making (especially at the highest levels of management) on the one hand, and the activities for their implementation on the other [8].

Thus, in the field of national security, a wide variety of information flows circulate, which are closely intertwined, superimposed on each other, in some way duplicate the content of the information being transferred. The study and optimization of these flows is a priority for improving the information security of national security.

Thus, the information function of the national security system consists in obtaining by the system as a whole and its elements of information necessary for the implementation of coordinated and purposeful activities to achieve the goals of national security.

Requirements for the execution of this function should be determined by the need and sufficiency of the information presented to the consumer in accordance with his requests - information needs and the possibilities of satisfying them. The issue of information needs of consumers of information in the field of national security, as in any other, is quite problematic and controversial.

We proceed from the fact that information needs derive from the functions of consumers and their role in ensuring national security and are formed on the basis of a modeling process to ensure the latter. This is explained by the fact that many hazards and threats can only be modeled (for example, information war, economic crisis, natural disasters, etc.) and, accordingly, can be modeled to neutralize or eliminate them.

References:

1. Panaryn Y.N. Ynformatsyonnaia voina y vlast. — M.: Yzdatelskyi dom «Myr bezopasnosty», 2001. - p.40
2. Obshchaia teoryia natsyonalnoi bezopasnosty / Pod obshch. red. A. A. Prokhozheva. — M.: Yzdatelstvo RAHS, 2005—344 p.
3. Lehasov V.A. Problemy bezopasnoho razvytyia tekhnosfery Entsyklopedyia / Pod red. V. A. Puchkova. — Moskva: FHBU VNYY HOChS (FTs), 2015. — T. 2: K—O. — p. 116. — 624 p.
4. Porfyrev B.N. Systemnaia kontseptsyia natsyonalnoi bezopasnosty. - M., 1995. p.11

5. Mukhyn H.V. Problema obespecheniya natsyonalnoi bezopasnosti v sovremennykh uslovyakh. - M.: VAKhT, 1994. p.27.
6. Vyner N. Kybernetyka y obshchestvo. - M.: Ynostrannaia lyteratura, 1958. p.31.
7. Berh A.Y., Byriukov B.V. Kybernetyka y prohress nauky y tekhniky / Sovremennoe estestvoznanye. - M.: Mysl, 1969. p.350.
8. Madera A. H. Rysky y shansy: neopredelennost, prohnozyrovanye y otsenka. — M.: URSS, 2014 — 448 p.